

**Newer View on Sustainable Development Through Biotechnology and
Socio-Economic Analysis**

Ankita Chawla¹, Sunita Bharatwal², Dhirendra Kumar^{3*}

¹Department of Economics, Chaudhary Bansi Lal University, Bhiwani, India, ²Department of Management, Chaudhary Bansi Lal University, Bhiwani, India, ³Department of Botany, Chaudhary Bansi Lal University, Bhiwani, India

Email: medhirendra01@gmail.com

The evolutionary biology interprets the capability to make choices in a fast-changing environment as a key adaptation. The ability to think about new problems and to choose under uncertain and unfamiliar conditions helps us to survive and reproduce. In this paper, stress has been laid on externalities (both positive and negative) and its implications for sustainability. Now as almost all the activities are being carried out in eco-friendly manner thereby promoting sustainability. Therefore, it becomes important to ascertain the reasonable implications of it on the generations to come. The presence of external effects that minimize environmental exposure are also an important issue in terms of sustainability. The relevance of this study is enhanced in recent times as many of the consumers as well as firms are becoming increasingly aware of the green practices being made and as a result there is increase in green enterprises. The present study also confirmed there is likelihood of people being attracted towards organic/green products. The findings of the study also revealed youth of the nation willing to pay extra amount in name of green practices followed by the enterprise; also, literacy remains a key factor in backing sustainability. Economics and Human Biology is devoted to the exploration of the effect of socio-economic processes on human beings as biological organisms. The effects of government intervention programs, as well as macroeconomic and public health policy on the human organism at either the individual or the population level. One aspect of biotechnology which has been used for centuries is the selective breeding of crop plants and farm animals to produce improved food. Its purpose is to educate people about biotechnology and its role in the socio-economic advancement and development of a nation so that they can make informed choices. Keywords: Sustainability, Green practices, Resources, Externalities, Organic foods, Ecofriendly